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Research Article

Problem Faced by Students During Research Work: A Cross-Sectional Study of Students at University Level

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Article Info.	Abstract
<p>Received: 30-June-24 Revised: 18-Sep-24 Accepted: 26-Sep-24 Published: 30-Sep-24</p>	<p>The study aimed to identify problems faced by university students during research work at the university level. The study was descriptive and used a survey method for data collection. The study population was 296 students at the university level. The sample size consisted of one hundred and seventeen (117). A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used as a research instrument to get the responses from the respondents. The researcher collected the data personally from the sample of the study. It was found that the researchers are facing problems in choosing a topic and choosing the right methodology, moreover choosing the right topic and methodology are crucial and challenging steps for the researchers. Feeling stressed and discouragement during research is a common challenge that faces researchers during the completion of the research project. The university may arrange proper training sessions for research projects and may develop a proper coordination mechanism between researchers and supervisors.</p>
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Introduction

The process of education begins at birth and lasts to death. Early life is extremely important because it shapes subsequent processes (Banks, 2013). Children are the main focus of the educational system from preschool through graduate school. Academic achievements primarily shift from group to individual as students advance to a higher grade level every year. For this reason, education is essential during a child's first ten or twelve years of life. If we were unable to teach them to be good citizens, then greater and higher social difficulties would arise (Nichols, 2017).

The words "re" and "search" are combined to form the word research. According to Singh (2022), the Oxford Dictionary defines "re" as "against," "over again," and "search" as a verb denoting attentive testing, examination, or problems. Once the two terms are combined, the noun "research" is created, denoting a systematic and careful evaluation conducted to expose information and identify the fundamental cause in any educational program. Furthermore, he clarifies that research is a systematic study conducted with the assistance of accepted scientific techniques in order to resolve issues and reveal broadly accepted advancements in the field. According to Andrade, Beirao, Arruda, & Cruz (2021) scientific method that includes systematic observation, classification, and data interpretation, research, possesses certain characteristics.

Ahmad, Shahid Khan, Wai Shiang, and Abdullah (2021) define research as a methodical, scientific investigation, particularly through the search for new information in any field of study. Conversely, education is viewed as the conclusion of all the processes through which people acquire the skills, attitudes, and other behavioral patterns necessary to maintain practical values in their communities (Banks, 2013). It's critical to recognize the importance of research in the classroom. The majority of people agree that research benefits individuals as well as the communities engaged in the educational system on a local, regional, national, and international level (Virtanen, 2016).

As stated, Empirical approaches are used in educational research, a type of systematic study, to address issues in education, solve issues, and produce knowledge, it uses exacting and well-defined scientific procedures for gathering and analyzing data. Best describes educational research as any action aimed at developing a science of behavior in educational settings. The vital purpose of such a science is to supply information that will allow the educator to attain his or her objectives using the most effective methods possible (Baloyi, 2016). The primary goal of educational research is to advance current understanding by finding answers to a range of pedagogical problems and enhancing methods of instruction. Finding solutions to issues with classroom management, student motivation, and growth is another area of interest for educational scholars.

Jeffrey (2016) asserts that research is critical to higher education. Everyone admits the importance of research to people's wealth and well-being in the present day. Gonzalez (2016) claims that research is involved in a wide range of activities, including the imagining and enhancement of knowledge, the modification of cultural norms, the resolution of various social issues, the enhancement of human potential, the extension of the limits of basic and social science knowledge, and the dissemination of concepts related to peace, democracy, and climate protection. Papanek (2022) states that research is not necessarily planned; rather, it is authorized by intelligent people working in a suitable environment.

Mehmetoglu & Jakobsen (2022) declare that new information is gathered systematically and scientifically through social science research, leading to the creation of new knowledge. The careful process by which new information on any social topic affecting individuals in society is

discovered is known as social science research. Researchers may better understand social events by doing social research, which helps them understand the why, when, where, what, and how of everyday social life construction and reconstruction (Hancock, Algozzine, & Lim, 2021).

The issues that university students had with their supervisors were frequent absences from work, tardiness in returning to work, and a lack of enthusiasm or competence in research. Time constraints, money issues, family issues, and library resources were major obstacles faced by students. The inability of the examined students to conduct research was severely influenced by all institution-related issues, a lack of internet access, a dearth of research-related courses, a lack of library resources, a lack of computer proficiency, and a lack of workshops.

There is a dearth of research on university-level research issues in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, but there are a few studies on the subject in Pakistan, such as one by Iqbal (2018) on the obstacles to postgraduate research in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's public and private universities. Therefore, researchers believe that more research needs to be done on the issues that students encounter when doing university-level research.

Review of Related Literature

Background of the Study

There are challenges that university students have when conducting research. According to the report, students had difficulties since they were unfamiliar with research techniques and did not get supervision. The study suggests that higher education institutions provide their students more direction and instruction in research technique (Wang, Yang, & Maresova, 2020). The challenges of research writing that university students must overcome. According to the survey, students often struggled with selecting a research subject, coming up with research questions, reviewing the literature, and analyzing data. According to the report, colleges should offer their students additional assistance in these areas (Ali & Zayid, 2022).

The problems encountered by university students when preparing research papers. According to the study, students had trouble choosing a research subject, writing, doing a literature review, and analyzing data. According to the survey, universities should give their students greater guidance and assistance with writing and research techniques (Dini, 2022).

Choosing the Right Topic

Selecting the appropriate study subject can be a crucial and difficult step in the research process. Recognize your interests by first learning about your hobbies and interests. Think about the parts of your field that attract you or the subjects that irritate your curiosity. When you are truly engaged in the topic matter, research becomes more enjoyable and motivating (Rose & Johnson, 2020).

Lack of Research Resources

Research resources is a major issue that many academics must deal with. Numerous instruments, such as packages, computers, study books, and research software, are included in these resources. Their limited availability creates significant barriers to the research process, making it more difficult for scientists to come up with research concepts, carry out in-depth analyses, and significantly advance their areas (Ghosh & Ray, 2023).

Lack of Research Packages

Research packages refer to customized software libraries, frameworks, or sets of instructions created to make particular research activities easier. Pre-implemented functions, data structures, and tools are frequently provided by these packages to help researchers handle, analyze, and professionally interpret their data. However, researchers could not have access to the required

study packages because of a variety of problems, including limited funds or restricted access. Their capacity to carry out complex analyses, perform simulations, or use cutting-edge techniques may be severely hampered by this shortage (Jacobsen, 2022).

Insufficient Laptop or Computing Resources

For researchers to complete resource-intensive operations like data processing, modeling, and simulation runs, a reliable and powerful laptop or computing system is essential. However, a researcher's capacity to carry out computationally intensive experiments or data analysis may be severely constrained by a lack of sufficient computer resources. Researchers may encounter prolonged processing times, restricted experimentation, and limited scalability without access to a powerful laptop or high-performance computing infrastructure, which would eventually hold down the advancement of their study (Silva & Pedro, 2023).

Inadequate Availability of Research Books

Research books are essential for giving critical understandings, theoretical frameworks, and in-depth knowledge on a wide range of research topics. These books are helpful resources that lead scholars through core ideas, approaches, and earlier research that is relevant to their field of study. Regretfully, there might not be as much access to study literature as there once was, especially in areas where universities, libraries, and specialty shops are hard to come by. Due to this shortage, researchers may find it more difficult to keep current on new developments, conduct literature reviews, and be exposed to a wider range of viewpoints (Oseghale & Osagie, 2023).

Limited Access to Research Software

Specialized computer programs for scientific investigation and analysis are referred to as research software. Researchers can examine and understand their findings more effectively because of the comprehensive statistical analysis, data visualization, and modeling capabilities that these programs frequently offer. However, researchers may encounter difficulties obtaining and using the tools required for their research due to fees, limitations, or the unavailability of specific software programs. This may lead to decreased output, spoiled data analysis, and lost chances for ground-breaking discoveries (Donoho, 2017).

One of the biggest problems facing researchers is the scarcity of research resources, such as packages, laptops, research literature, and research software. Lack of access to these essential resources limits the possibilities for ground-breaking discoveries and hinders the research process and knowledge development. To ensure that researchers have fair access to the instruments and materials needed to push the limits of scientific investigation, efforts must be taken to alleviate these resource restrictions (Brown & Duenas, 2022).

Lack of Financial Resources

Research makes an effort to discover many domains and is a crucial foundation of knowledge production and scientific progression. However, the scarcity of funding is one of the biggest issues facing scholars. Inadequate financing presents difficulty in delaying researchers' ability to carry out comprehensive studies, get essential tools and supplies, and explore original concepts. In addition to having an impact on specific scholars, this lack of funding has larger consequences for the advancement of society at large (Beuscher, 2022).

Limited Travel and Collaboration Opportunities

To share knowledge, pool resources, and take advantage of a variety of skills, collaboration and knowledge sharing are essential components of the research process. Financial limitations, however, may make it difficult for academics to travel to other universities for research trips or conferences. Insufficient funds might inhibit networking possibilities and restrict joint projects with other scholars and organizations. As a result, it might be difficult for researchers to get the

critical feedback, new views, and possible research collaborations that they need to development of their work (Henderson, & Dancy, 2008).

Time Management

Students frequently struggle with time management when working on research assignments. These are some particular issues with time management that students could run across. Delay of respondents may put off beginning their research project, which would leave them with insufficient time to do assignments efficiently. Numerous things, like feeling overwhelmed, lacking interest, or having trouble starting, might contribute to delay. Inadequate assignment of priority of respondents could find it difficult to properly manage their time and prioritize their responsibilities. If people don't set clear priorities, they could spend too much time on insignificant things and overlook vital ones (Boss, & Krauss, 2022).

Lack of Knowledge and Understanding of Research

For students working on research projects, a lack of expertise and comprehension of research might present serious difficulties. According to Henderson (2019) here are some typical problems with this task and solutions for them that are insufficient knowledge of research procedures Understanding many research procedures and choosing the best one for their topic might be difficult for students. They can overcome this by reading books, articles, or internet resources on research techniques as part of their self-study. It might also be helpful to ask knowledgeable researchers or faculty members for advice.

Insufficient knowledge about research design Important choices about variables, sample size, data collection techniques, and statistical analyses must be made while designing a research study. It might be challenging for students to plan their studies well. They can learn more by participating in research design courses or workshops, speaking with academics, or working with seasoned researchers (Bell & Waters, 2018).

Lack of Communication with Supervisor

It might be difficult and perhaps harmful to your workplace if you don't communicate with your supervisor. It is vital to tackle this matter and devise strategies for establishing efficient channels of communication. The following actions are what you can do. After giving it some thought, determine if the lack of communication is a persistent problem or a one-time event. Consider any reasonable explanations for the lack of communication, such as a demanding schedule or competing priorities. Take the initiative to reach out to your supervisor, ask to have a talk, or arrange a meeting. Make it clear that you are concerned about the lack of communication and how it is affecting your job. Have an optimistic and helpful attitude when you enter the discussion (Chandoli & Anastasiou, 2020).

When talking about the lack of communication, be precise and give examples. Describe specific times when you felt accepted or did not have the information you needed to finish your job efficiently. This will assist your supervisor in appreciating the seriousness of the problem and offer specific suggestions for change. Clearly state your expectations for communication and state your needs. Talk about your preferred method of communication (email, in-person meetings, etc.), how frequently you would like to get updates, and any special information you need to do your work well (Klasen, 2010). Ask for clarification and comments. Take advantage of this chance to get clarity on any questions. Ask for input on your performance as well as areas that need work. This might encourage more open conversation and demonstrate your dedication to professional development. Investigate alternate routes of communication. If face-to-face meetings or emails aren't working, try suggesting another channel that could be more convenient for you and your supervisor. Project management software, instant messaging programs, and frequent check-ins are

a few examples of this (Lindgreen, Di Benedetto, Clarke, Ewald, Bjorn-Andersen, & Lambert, 2021).

Difficulty in Keeping Up with the Teaching Job

If you're finding it difficult to keep up with your teaching duties, it's critical to address the issues you're having and look into more efficient time management techniques. Consider the particular sides of your teaching profession that are giving you trouble. Is it the amount of work, lesson preparation, assessment, classroom organization, or something else entirely? Recognizing the difficulties will enable you to develop focused solutions.

Bartlet, Arslan, Bankston, and Sarabipour (2021) state that make a list of all of your duties and obligations, then order them according to significance and urgency. High-priority activities should be finished first to guarantee that all necessary work is completed; less important tasks can be handled later. Create a methodical strategy for handling your task. Divide more complex jobs into smaller, more possible pieces, and make a timetable or calendar to provide time for certain activities each week. Reducing overload and maintaining focus may be achieved via efficient planning and organization. Give some jobs or obligations to trustworthy students, teaching assistants, or coworkers if at all possible. By splitting up the effort, you'll be able to concentrate on your core teaching responsibilities and lessen your load. Furthermore, don't be afraid to ask for help from administrators, mentors, or other educators who may offer direction and counsel (Fry, 2007).

Need for Collaboration with Other Institution

Collaboration with other institutions can be highly beneficial during the research process, as it allows researchers to leverage different expertise, resources, and perspectives to address complex problems and bridge knowledge gaps. However, there can be challenges that arise when seeking collaboration with other institutions. Identifying suitable collaborators, and finding the right institutions and researchers to collaborate with can be a challenge. Start by networking within your field, attending conferences, and reaching out to colleagues or mentors who may have connections to other institutions. Explore online platforms or databases that facilitate collaboration and connect researchers with similar interests (Bell & Mezler, 2021).

Research Objectives

1. To identify the problems faced by the students during research work at the university level.
2. To compare the problems faced by the BS Level students and M.Phil. Level students.

Research Methodology

This study was descriptive and the survey method was used to find out the problems faced by the university students during the research work at the university level. Forty students (40) of B. Ed (Hons) Elementary level of the Department of Education, 40 students of BS level of the Department of Economics, 34 students of BS level of the Department of Banking and Finance, 40 students of BS level of the Department of Physics, 40 students of BS level of the Department of Biotechnology, 40 students of BS level of the Department of Botany University of Kotli, Azad Jammu and Kashmir were the population of the study. In this way, the total population was 296. Twenty students 20 of B. Ed (Hons) Elementary level from the Department of Education, 20 students of BS level from the Department of Economics, 17 students of BS level from the Department of Banking and Finance, 20 students of BS level from the Department of Physics, 20 students of BS level from the Department of Biotechnology, 20 students of BS level were selected from the department of Botany. In this way, the sample was 117. A questionnaire used as a research instrument to collect data from the university students. The questionnaire based on the problems faced by the university students during the research work at the university level. There

were 48 statements in the questionnaire. The researcher collected the data personally from the University of Kotli students. The data analyzed through the statistical package for social sciences software (SPSS). It was helpful in understanding the relation between the variables. The data obtained from the sample was tabulated and analyzed by using Mean, standard deviation, and other statistical measures.

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of lack of interest

Statements	N	Mean
Feeling stressed during research is a common challenge.	117	4.37
Topic without the choice of researcher causes lack of interest in the research students	117	4.25
Choosing the right topic is a crucial and challenging step in research	117	4.25
A non-supportive attitude of family discourages students from completing research	117	3.98
Family responsibilities impacts negatively research activities	117	3.86
Lack of student support in research work discourage to complete the research work	117	3.82

Table 1 shows the mean scores of lack of interest. The table further represented that mean score of Feeling stressed during research is a common challenge; N= 117, M=4.37, Topic without the choice of researcher causes lack of interest in the research students; N=117, M= 4.25, Choosing the right topic is a crucial and challenging step in research; N=117, M=4.25, Non-supportive attitude of family discourages students from completing research; N=117, M=3.98, Family responsibilities impacts negatively research activities; N=117, M=3.98, and Family responsibilities impacts negatively research activities; N=117; M= 3.82. Furthermore, the results directed that Feeling stressed during research is a common challenge has the highest mean score in lack of Interest.

Table 2

Mean Analysis of Lack of Knowledge and Understanding of Research

Statements	N	Mean
Lack of knowledge of research tools creates problems in the completion of research work	117	3.93
Researchers lack the competency to start the computer	117	3.56
Researchers lack the skill to transfer data to other devices	117	3.57
Researchers are unable to create data sheet	117	3.54
Researchers are unfamiliar with cut / copy and paste	117	3.54
Lack of research experience causes problems in conducting research	117	3.55

Table 2 shows the mean scores of lack of knowledge and understanding of research. The table further represented that mean score of Lack of knowledge of research tools creates problems in the completion of research work; N= 117, M=3.93, Researchers lack the competency to start the computer; N=117, M= 3.56, Researchers lack the skill to transfer data to other devices; N=117,

M=3.57, Researchers are unable to create data sheet; N=117, M=3.57, Researchers are unfamiliar with cut / copy and paste; N=117, M=3.54, and Lack of research experience causes problems in conducting research; N=117; M= 3.55. Furthermore, the results directed that Lack of knowledge of research tools creates problems in the completion of research work has the highest mean score in lack of knowledge and understanding of research.

Table 3
Mean Analysis of Limited Access to Research Software

Statements	N	Mean
Discouragement during research work is a common challenge	117	3.64
Research projects require time to draw meaningful conclusions	117	3.71
Research variables are not managed by the researchers	117	3.74
Choosing the right methodology is a crucial and challenging step in research project	117	3.69
Domestic responsibilities of the researcher results into late submission of their project work	117	3.80
Researchers face issues in buying laptops for research projects	117	4.19
Researchers face troubles to have internet packages till the completion of their research work	117	4.19
Researchers feel burden to buy expensive USBs	117	3.55
Limited access to research software can create problems in research work	117	3.48
Cost of research books can delay in completion of a research project	117	3.62

Table 3 shows the mean scores of limited access to research software. The table further represented that mean score of Discouragement during research work is a common challenge; N= 117, M=3.64, Research projects require time to draw meaningful conclusions; N=117, M= 3.71, Research variables are not managed by the researchers; N=117, M=3.74, Choosing the right methodology is a crucial and challenging step in research project; N=117, M=3.69, Domestic responsibilities of the researcher results into late submission of their project work; N=117, M=3.80, Researchers face issues in buying laptops for research projects; N=117; M= 4.19, Researchers face troubles to have internet packages till the completion of their research work; N=117; M= 4.19, Researchers feel burden to buy expensive USBs; N=117; M= 3.55, Limited access to research software can create problems in research work; N=117; M= 3.48, and Cost of research books can delay in completion of a research project; N=117; M= 3.62. Furthermore, the results directed that Researchers face issues in buying laptops for research projects has the highest mean score in limited access to research software.

Table 4
Mean analysis of financial resources

Statements	N	Mean
Financial problems of researchers affect negatively his/her research work	117	3.35
Traveling for data collection affect negatively research work	117	3.35
The data collection process is expensive for researchers	117	3.21
Researchers face financial burdens in printing and binding of thesis	117	3.67
Researchers suffer isolation because of his/her engagement in research activities	117	3.83

Researchers suffer isolation because of his/her engagement in research activities	117	3.81
Respondents delay to provide data which results into late submission of research work	117	3.83
Lack of interest of respondents in the provision of data discourages the researcher	117	3.82
Lack of interest of respondents negatively impact research work	117	3.66
The working environment at the workplace negatively affects the student's research schedule	117	3.62
Lack of understanding of peer groups also negatively affect the research work.	117	3.69

Table 4 shows the mean scores of financial resources. The table further represented that mean score of Financial problems of researchers affect negatively his/her research work; N= 117, M=3.35, Traveling for data collection affect negatively research work; N=117, M= 3.35, The data collection process is expensive for researchers; N=117, M=3.21, Researchers face financial burdens in printing and binding of thesis; N=117, M=3.67, Researchers suffer isolation because of his/her engagement in research activities; N=117, M=3.83, Researchers suffer isolation because of his/her engagement in research activities; N=117; M= 3.81, Respondents delay to provide data which results into late submission of research work; N=117; M= 3.83, Lack of interest of respondents in the provision of data discourages the researcher; N=117; M= 3.82, Lack of interest of respondents negatively impact research work; N=117; M= 3.66, The working environment at the workplace negatively affects the student's research schedule; N=117; M= 3.62 and Lack of understanding of peer groups also negatively affect the research work; N=117; M= 3.69. Furthermore, the results directed that Respondents delay to provide data which results into late submission of research work has the highest mean score in financial resources.

Table 5

Mean analysis of social hurdle

Statements	N	Mean
No cooperative behavior of officials during data collection discourage researchers	117	3.78
Social hurdles of the researcher negatively affect the research work	117	3.73
There is a communication gap between the supervisor and supervisee which creates hurdles in the completion of research	117	4.06
The non-cooperative behavior of the supervisor causes frustration among students	117	3.99
Rude behavior of supervisor can cause to lose researchers, interest in the project	117	3.82
Non-availability of a supervisor discourages students from completing his/her research work	117	3.79
Guidance and counseling services are available for students	117	3.83
The supervisor is available in the department to guide the students as and when needed	117	3.80
Heavy load work of the supervisor is a reason for the lack of communication between supervisor and supervise	117	3.74

Cooperation between supervisor and supervisee enhances researcher performance	117	3.78
Delay in contacting the supervisor causes late submission of research project	117	3.75
Additional duties of the supervisor causes late completion of research Work	117	3.81

Table 5 shows the mean scores of social hurdle. The table further represented that mean score of No cooperative behavior of officials during data collection discourage researchers; N=117, M=3.78, Social hurdles of the researcher negatively affect the research work; N=117, M=3.73, There is a communication gap between the supervisor and supervisee which creates hurdles in the completion of research; N=117, M=4.06, The non-cooperative behavior of the supervisor causes frustration among students; N=117, M=3.99, Rude behavior of supervisor can cause to lose researchers, interest in the project; N=117, M=3.82, Non-availability of a supervisor discourages students from completing his/her research work; N=117; M= 3.79, Guidance and counseling services are available for students; N=117; M= 3.83, The supervisor is available in the department to guide the students as and when needed; N=117; M= 3.80, Heavy load work of the supervisor is a reason for the lack of communication between supervisor and supervisee; N=117; M= 3.74, Cooperation between supervisor and supervisee enhances researcher performance; N=117; M= 3.78, Delay in contacting the supervisor causes late submission of research project; N=117; M= 3.74 and Additional duties of the supervisor causes late completion of research Work; N=117; M= 3.81. Furthermore, the results directed that There is a communication gap between the supervisor and supervisee which creates hurdles in the completion of research and has the highest mean score in social hurdle.

Discussion

The challenges faced by researchers during a research project are multifaceted and can significantly impact both the process and the quality of the outcomes. The first challenge of selecting an appropriate topic and methodology is a critical decision that defines the research's direction. Research indicates that this initial step is often stressful because it requires balancing personal interests, relevance to the field, and feasibility within resource and time constraints (Maxwell, 2020). Furthermore, selecting the correct methodology can be overwhelming for researchers unfamiliar with various research designs and statistical methods (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). These difficulties are compounded by the emotional toll research can take, with stress and discouragement being common, particularly when researchers encounter setbacks or feel uncertain about their progress.

Technological competencies, or the lack thereof, present another significant hurdle. Researchers often struggle with basic computer skills, such as starting a computer, managing files, and performing data-related tasks, which can slow down the research process (Selwyn, 2019). These gaps in digital literacy are particularly problematic given the increasing reliance on technology for data collection, analysis, and presentation in contemporary research.

Family responsibilities and financial constraints further complicate the research experience. Balancing family duties with the demanding schedule of a research project often results in reduced focus and productivity, as noted in studies exploring work-life balance in academia (Misra et al., 2021). Additionally, financial challenges—such as the cost of purchasing

laptops, internet packages, and essential tools like USB drives—can create significant obstacles for researchers. Limited access to these resources hampers their ability to gather and analyze data effectively, leading to delays in producing meaningful results (Altbach & de Wit, 2020).

Isolation is another common challenge for researchers, particularly as they become deeply engaged in their work. The intense focus required for research can lead to feelings of detachment from family, friends, and colleagues, causing emotional distress (Brewster & Clark, 2019). This isolation is exacerbated when researchers encounter non-cooperative respondents or officials, which can lead to frustration and discouragement. Without access to supportive networks or collaborative opportunities, researchers may struggle to maintain motivation and momentum throughout the research process.

The financial strain of conducting research, alongside these other challenges, creates a compounding effect that can negatively impact the quality and timeliness of the research. Financial difficulties limit access to necessary resources and, as a result, prolong the time needed to complete the project. Studies have shown that inadequate funding and material resources are among the most significant barriers to successful research, particularly for early-career researchers (Bentley & Kyvik, 2019).

Conclusions

1. The researchers face problems in choosing a topic and the right methodology, moreover choosing the right topic and methodology are crucial and challenging steps for the researchers.
2. Feeling stressed and discouragement during research is a common challenge that faces researchers during the completion of the research project.
3. Researchers lack the competency of how to start a computer, save files, and create data sheets. Moreover, researchers are unfamiliar with cutting/copying and pasting data.
4. Family responsibilities affect the researchers' performance.
5. Researcher requires time to draw meaningful results. The researchers face problems in buying laptops, having an internet package, and expensive USBs till the completion of the research.
6. Financial problems of the researchers affect negatively the research project.
7. Researchers feel isolated due to their engagement in research and this isolation causes distress. Non-cooperative behaviors of respondents and officials in the provision of data cause discouragement for the researchers.
8. Researchers feel isolated due to their engagement in research and this isolation causes distress.

Recommendations

1. The university may arrange proper training sessions for research projects and may develop a proper coordination mechanism between researchers and supervisors.
2. The researchers might carefully consider their interests and may adjust them according to the research framework to avoid stress and discouragement and to ensure a successful and impactful study.
3. The researchers may receive basic computer literacy training and improve their competency in computer skills.
4. Researchers may accommodate their social responsibilities and utilize their resources according to their budgets to avoid the effect of responsibilities on performance.
5. Researchers need to invest sufficient time and effort in their work to yield meaningful results, and this commitment might be attained by committed and hard-working individuals.

6. Researchers may avail the opportunities of gaining laptops or scholarships to fulfill their requirements regarding their project and also try to manage with the internet package available in the university and also gain help from relevant departments or funding sources to overcome these hurdles.
7. University, academic institutions, and funding organizations may work together to address the researcher's issues and provide resources and platforms for networking, sharing experiences, and seeking emotional support within the research community.
8. Future researchers may conduct studies focusing on the problems regarding topic Selection, Literature review, Methodology, and Analysis.

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